

Stress tolerance—adverse temperature

Cold tolerance of Yunnan rices at early seedling stage

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We screened 2,763 local Yunnan rice varieties for cold tolerance at the early seedling stage during 1987-89. Healthy germinating seeds (100/variety) were chilled at 5 °C for 10 d, then put under sunlight for 10 d. Recovery was assessed on a 1-9 scale, where 1 = highly resistant, 3 = resistant, 5 = medium resistant, 7 = susceptible, 9 = highly susceptible.

We found only 19 highly resistant varieties (less than 3% of those tested). Fifteen originated in Jinping and Shangjiang counties, 2 upland varieties in Changyuan county.

Japonica-lowland-glutinous rice has the best cold tolerance; indica-lowland-

glutinous, the least. Although indica-upland rices had the lowest score and indica-lowland the highest, in general japonicas have significantly greater cold tolerance than indicas, upland rices greater tolerance than lowland, and

nonglutinous greater than glutinous.

The table gives paired comparisons of cold tolerance among 12 forms. The difference in cold tolerance between japonica and indica holds up, but that between lowland and upland and between nonglutinous and glutinous is only partly substantiated. □

Paired comparison of cold tolerance among 12 rice forms in Yunnan, China.

Form	Varieties (no.)	Cold tolerance (av score)	U-value ^a
Indica-upland	17	6.29	1.80
Indica-lowland	1756	8.12	
Japonica-lowland	700	7.25	
Japonica-upland	290	7.46	
Lowland-glutinous	1853	7.94	5.66**
Lowland-nonglutinous	603	7.69	
Upland-nonglutinous	123	7.55	
Upland-glutinous	184	7.28	
Indica-glutinous	1448	8.11	11.45**
Indica-nonglutinous	325	8.07	
Japonica-nonglutinous	401	7.33	
Japonica-glutinous	589	7.30	

^a Significant at 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels.

Comparative performance of indigenous rice varieties for cold tolerance in the hills of Nepal

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Injury due to cold temperature occurs at different stages of rice crop growth in different areas of Nepal, depending on altitude and temperature of irrigation water. Screening of exotic materials from the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery at Lumle (1,400 m) has not been promising: most entries showed good cold tolerance at seedling and vegetative stage but failed to produce grain because of incomplete panicle exertion or spikelet sterility. Delayed heading, degeneration of spikelet tips,

and chaffiness of panicles are common symptoms in wetland rice transplanted in Jul above 1,400 m elevation.

Indigenous rice varieties Chhomrong, Seto Bhakunde, and Himali Marshi had performed well at Lumle. We collected 79 indigenous varieties from Lumle and Pakhribas Research Command areas, with altitudes from 700 to 2,000 m asl, and evaluated them at Lumle for cold tolerance and agronomic traits at vegetative and reproductive stages. Mean tempera-

tures at Lumle fall below 20 °C toward the beginning of the reproductive phase (Table 1). Forty-one genotypes showed good cold tolerance at the reproductive stage. Data for the 10 best entries are given in Table 2.

These indigenous germplasm also show good tolerance for diseases associated with low temperature (neck blast *Pyricularia oryzae* and sheath rot *Acrocyndrium oryzae*).

Most materials collected from above

Table 1. Meteorological data for Lumle (28°N 83°E) in 1990.

Month	Av temperature (°C)				Relative humidity (%)	Total rainfall (mm)	Av sunshine (h)
	Max	Min	Mean	Water ^a			
May	23.3	14.6	19.0	NR	82.4	325	5.7
Jun	24.7	17.1	20.9	NR	92.2	1107	4.2
Jul	24.0	17.6	20.8	22.0	97.3	1407	2.1
Aug	23.7	17.4	20.6	20.8	95.2	1088	2.7
Sep	23.5	16.6	20.1	19.6	92.5	978	4.1
Oct	21.1	12.2	16.7	17.8	81.2	315	8.6
Nov	19.3	11.4	15.2	NR	72.3	0	9.3
Mean	22.8	15.3	19.0	20.1	87.6	-	5.2
Total						5220	36.7

^a NR = not recorded.